

Paper 9**AN EXPLORATORY STUDY ON THE HOLISTIC WELFARE OF ELDERLY IN MANGALURU****Jeevan¹ & Pradeep M.D²**¹ II Year M.S.W, Institute of Social Sciences & Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka. Email: jeevan.jj99@gmail.com² Associate Professor, Institute of Social Sciences & Humanities, Srinivas University, Mangaluru, Karnataka Email: mdpradeepnair767@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Old age though is not precisely chronological age, it is a universal phenomenon and a challenge to everyone, who reaches it irrespective of occupation, skill or learning. Individuals survive childhood, grow to maturity and become old in all societies. Several factors such as biological, psychological, social, and ecological factors influence aging. This old age is characterized by poor adjustment, sense of time and sense of life cycle; desire to leave a legacy, neurological and sensory changes, and change of roles and period of decline. As an individual attains the stage of old age all the organs and tissues of the body start degenerating. The rate at which degeneration occurs does not strictly follow the chronological age. Today, the old age homes are indispensable as they are needed to take care of the lonely and forsaken elderly in the evening of their lives. Nowadays, old age homes are established to take care of the old. This idea of “institutionalization” of the aged has largely been borrowed from the western countries. However, in recent times, as a result of the demographic transition, the rapid pace of industrialization and urbanization, the disintegration of joint family structures into nuclear ones, increasing participation of families in the non-agricultural labor force, the older people have become more vulnerable. The lack of familial support made elderly resort to old age homes run by private and or voluntary organizations for their care and support. Of the several consequences of such trends, one that causes serious concern is that of providing care to a large number of older persons to have a better quality of life.

Key Words: Old Age, Geriatric, Elderly, Gerontology, Older Adults.

1. INTRODUCTION

Vast majority of the elder population in India live in rural area, 90 percent are from unorganized sector with no social security, 30 percent live below poverty line and another 33 percent just marginally over it. According to Population Census 2011 there are nearly 104 million elderly persons (aged 60 years or above) in India; 53 million females and 51 million males. A report released by the United Nations Population Fund and HelpAge India suggests that the number of elderly persons is expected to grow to 173 million by 2026. According to the Report of the Technical Group on Population Projections for India and States 2011-2036, there are nearly 138 million elderly persons in India in 2021 (67 million males and 71 million females) and is further expected to increase by around 56 million elderly persons in 2031. Both the share and size of elderly population is increasing over time. From 5.6% in 1961 the proportion has increased to 8.6% in 2011. The proportion has increased to 10.1% in 2021 and further likely to increase to 13.1% in 2031. For males it was marginally lower at 8.2%, while for females it was 9.0%. It is

interesting to note that upto Population Census 1991, the number of elderly females exceeded the number of elderly males. However, in the last two decades, the trend has been reversed and the elderly males outnumbered the elderly females. Further, it is projected that the number of elderly females will exceed the number of males in 2031. As regards rural and urban areas, as per 2011 census, 71% of elderly population resides in rural areas while 29 % is in urban areas. Important nomenclatures used are described below.

(i) Voluntary Organization for Aged: There is numerous voluntary organization and India and Age – Care India, in particular, to know about the kind of activities are carrying on in the field of the care of the aged.

(ii) Old Age Homes: The central or state governments, Municipal Bodies, philanthropic Societies, Voluntary Organization and Senior Citizens Welfare Association have set up homes for old or elderly citizens to provide them residential facilities and other allied needs, entertainment places to have physical and mental activities, creativity to combat loneliness and to have contacts and interaction with other people. At present, there are only some 300 homes in the country mostly in urban areas.

(iii) The Right to Refuse Admission: No older person can be placed in residential care without their consent unless their mental conditions render them incapable. In such cases, consent must be given by people authorized by the law to do so.

(iv) Institutionalization: In case of the aged need institutionalization, it is the social worker who should help determine the suitability of the person for admission to the institution by conducting home visits and interviews with the aged and the family. Shifting an elderly to an institution means adjustments with the changed environment and that is not an easy process.

(v) Pensions Portal: A Pension Portal has been set up by the Department of Pensions, Government of India, to enable senior citizens to get information regarding the status of their application, the amount of pension, documents required, if any, etc. The Portal also provides for lodging of grievances.

2. METHODOLOGY

(a) Objectives of the Study: To Study the socio demographic status of elderly, To Study the issues and challenges of elderly in Mangaluru, To Study the level of awareness on the benefits available for the Elderly, To Study the opportunities of engaging elderly in the Nation Building, to study the magnitude of elderly abuse

(b) Statement of Problem: The elderly constitutes the largest single group utilizing Personal Social Services worldwide. The care of elderly has become one of the biggest social concern since they are no longer live independently. As part of the process of finding eldercare solutions, there is a need to find ways to assess elders' needs, locating care resources which addresses these needs, and managing financial and legal considerations associated with transitioning to old age. The help and support the elders need to face their stress arising out of their age. In all advanced industrial societies, the proportion of infirm elderly is on the increase, and although they constitute only a small minority of the retired population, their claim on the holistic welfare and the social services is disproportionately heavy. So, this study is done to find solutions for the problems of the elderly for their holistic welfare.

(c) Scope of the Study: This study is conducted to understand the issues, challenges, level of awareness and the abuses faced by elderly population of Mangaluru. This study will help to understand holistic welfare of elderly population of Mangaluru and also help the researchers

have a better understanding of the holistic welfare of the elderly population of the particular area and various other determinants of it.

(d) Research Design: The Research design is exploratory, and the data has been compiled using questionnaire

(e) Sources of Data Collection: Primary Data- The investigator collected data through Interview method. Secondary Data- The secondary data refers to the data which already been collected by the someone else and which has been published.

(f) Universe of the Study: Universe of the study is the total population covered for this study. The study covers the elderly population of Mangaluru taluk of Dakshina Kannada district. Since the size of study population was big, researcher has chosen convenient sampling technique to decide upon the sample size. The researcher has collected the data from 100 respondents who are accessible easily in the study area.

(g) Inclusive Criteria: Elderly population of Mangaluru, Elderly population living in non institutionalized settings

(h) Exclusive Criteria: Elderly population of other taluks than Mangaluru, Elderly population living in the institutionalized settings in Mangaluru.

3. LITERATURE SURVEY

Easterlin (2005) himself reassessed his earlier findings and projected that happiness depends on 2 kinds of factors: monetary and non-pecuniary. monetary factors are those to which individuals will utterly adapt, like income; non-pecuniary factors are those that, like disability, semipermanent state and wedding can cause long-term changes within the individual's well-being. According to Walker (2005) the phenomenon, referred to as the satisfaction contradiction in terms or "stability despite loss" paradox, tries to clarify the disconnect inherent within the comparatively high levels of subjective life satisfaction according by older living in objectively comparatively unhealthy conditions. it's noted that this supposed contradiction in terms can be caused by age-cohort effects – that is, older folks might report higher levels of life satisfaction thanks to the lower expectations of a selected generation The demographic changes according to Coughlin and D'ambrosio (2009) that arose with the Baby Boomers (people born in 50 s) overcomes general convictions towards elderly financial planning taken as the basis for the marketing activities of the companies in the financial sector. According to McKenna, K., Broome, K., Liddle, J (2007) analyzing the older person in an exceedingly holistic care approach can lower physical incapacity, along with social disability and will increase his/her life satisfaction. The literature on subjective well-being by Diener (2009) cares with however and why folks' expertise their lives in positive ways, together with each psychological feature judgments and emotional reactions. As such, it covers studies that have used such various terms as happiness, satisfaction, morale, and positive affect Overall satisfaction with life is usually measured mistreatment the Satisfaction with Life Scale (SWLS) by Diener (2009) this scale asks respondents to that extent they believe 5 statements, together with i'mglad with my life. Responses are given on a seven-point scale, starting from powerfully disagree to strongly agree. According to World Health Organization (2010) Aging may be a constant, natural and inevitable method in living creatures' lives, characterized by biopsychosocial and cultural changes that are full of intrinsic factors reminiscent of biology and by foreign factors such as nonheritable experiences and also the environment. Study by Azaiza (2010) found higher death anxiety among those in care institutions than those who were not. Also noted, institutional residence

may actually be the result of physical or psychological problems and lack of an informal support system has been postulated as a reason for entering institutional care and found to be a correlate of death anxiety among elderly persons in care facilities. The statistical division of the United National Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) together with the European Commission (EC) and an expert group developed an Active Ageing Index (AAI) (2012) which measures elderly's potential for active and healthy ageing in four domains: (1) employment, (2) participation in society (including voluntary activities, care of children and grandchildren, care of older adults and political participation), (3) independent, healthy and secure living and (4) capacity and enabling environment for active ageing. Argyle (2013) found proof that happiness will increase slightly with age, chiefly due to a declining goal-achievement gap. In different words, as time goes by, individuals understand that their expectations were most likely set too high in their younger years and learn to simply accept the fact of their lives. Barusch (2013) have defined our current demographic scenario as a "grey tsunami": an increasingly ageing population resulting from greater life expectancy, wellness, and scientific progress. Gamble (2015) in his paper said that cognitive changes, when associated with ageing, may influence the financial decision-making capabilities of the elderly. Mather (2019) in his paper after speculation said that in several countries, people aged 65 and older currently represent a quarter of the total population. According to Asebedo (2019) older people usually control a large part of families' financial stock and hold higher purchasing power; as such, they significantly contribute to consumption Negi, D. S. (2022) in their paper Global food price surge, in-kind transfers and household welfare: Evidence from India have found that for welfare and betterment of the older persons, we should target the protection of already existing social support systems/traditional social establishments resembling family and kinship, neighborhood bonding, community bonding and community participation must be revived and kins ought to show sensitivity towards older adults.

4. PROBLEMS OF ELDERLY

Physical disability in the aged often gives rise to profound anxiety and a sense of apathy and helplessness. This situation is indeed very difficult, since the aged in such conditions invariably tend to be withdrawn, negative and inflexible. In such situation, the elderly requires a lot of physical and emotional support especially from the family or loved ones. When it comes to corrections, women resist more than the men. Hence, it tends to alienate and push the elderly, especially women into a cycle of depression and social isolation. With the breakdown of traditions and family structures in many societies increasing numbers of elderly live alone or in home for the aged. Some of the social problems normally faced by the elderly persons include lack of contacts with friends, lowering of socioeconomic status, i.e., loss or decreased source of income may lead to inferiority complex for elderly in the society, incapability to involve himself in happier or sad moments of relatives, education and upbringing of children along with their settlement, feeling of isolation and neglect by children especially when the partner is no more. All these problems are likely to erode or damage the social status of an elderly person to a great extent. a) Physical Problems b) Mental Problems c) Family Problems d) Feminizations of Aging e) Discrimination f) Dependency g) Authoritative Problems h) Social Dignity i) Religion j) Generational Gap

(a) Causes for Problems: Common conditions that contribute to a change of interest and recreational activities include physical, psychological and lifestyle changes in elderly and changes in interests. When they are in good physical condition, elderly people are often preoccupied with their health and with the bodily process. Frequently they tend to complain about their health and to exaggerate even the simplest ailment they have. The areas the elderly get affected with are, a) Health b) Economic status c) Marital status d) Living conditions e) Compulsory retirement f) Hiring policies g) Pension plans h) Values i) Social status

(b) Psychological Reactions: The common psychological reactions of the elderly are a) Anxiety b) Anger and Irritability c) Apathy d) Paranoid Reactions e) Sadness and depression

5. MEASURES FOR ELDERLY WELFARE

Old age is a sensitive phase elderly people need care and comfort to lead a healthy life without worries and anxiety. Lack of awareness on the changing behavioral patterns in elderly cause to their abuse by their kin. Birth, childhood, adolescence, adulthood and old age are the crucial stages of human life, with its own issues and concerns. As each level passes, physical strength deteriorates and mental stability reduces. However, for many caring elder people is not possible due to work priorities. Elders suffering from cognitive challenges experience serious personality changes which need attention. The unattended elders suffer rejection, purposelessness and may turn to be violent. Regardless aging as a natural progression it carries problems. Welfare of elderly, is mandated by the Constitution of India. Constitutional safeguards on old age security, public assistance, pension, establishing old age homes, geriatric services and liberalized housing policy. Right to equality shall be guaranteed as a fundamental right. Social Security is vested with Central and State Governments. The United Nations Principles for Older Persons adopted by the United Nation General Assembly in 1991, Proclamation of Aging and the Global Targets on Aging for the year 2001 adopted by the General assembly in 1992 and other resolutions from time to time encouraged government to design their own policies and programmes. The government introduced Old Age Pension Schemes. Many need decent living conditions and quality care. India formulated several policies in response to the International efforts on ageing by World health Organisation (WHO), recommendations of The Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), Resolution on Older Women, January 2010, The United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) constituting Knowledge base on Population Ageing in India (BKPAI), International Labour Organisation (ILO) works on Income Security & Social Pensions, Result of Longitudinal Ageing Study in India (LASI) etc. Upon the United Nations declaring 1999 as the International Year of Older Persons, On 13th January, 1999, The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment, Government of India adopted National Policy on Older persons to constitute Pension Fund for the security of Unorganised sector, Construction of old age homes, day care centers in 3-4 districts, establishing resource centers, reemployment bureau for the elderly, 30 % concession in train and 50 % in Airlines and establishing compulsory Geriatric Care facility in Public Hospitals. The National Institute of Social Defence (NISD) set up in 1961 and acquired autonomous status in 2002 to work for the welfare of senior citizens along with prevention of drug use, begging and deal with the issues of transgender community. The Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment identified well performing NGOs designating them to be the Regional Resource Training Centres and provides fund to work as collaborating partners in providing effective delivery of age care services. The Ministry of Corporate Affairs, Government of India has notified Section 135 of the Companies

Act, 2013 along with Companies (Corporate Social Responsibility Policy) Rules, 2014 to support initiatives to improve the lives of Senior citizens by establishing old age homes, day care centres and other facilities to reduce the inequalities faced by social and economically backward groups. The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007 provides legal sanctions to the rights of the elders. An Affirmative Situation Analysis of the Elderly 2011 was conducted by the Government Departments to review the utilities of existing public services including financial security, health care, shelter, education, welfare, protection of life and property of the Senior Citizens. Hindu Personal laws declared the care of elderly as the moral duty of Children. Section 20 of the Hindu Adoption and Maintenance Act, 1956 specifies that children are liable to maintain the parents who are unable to maintain themselves. Under Muslim Personal Law, Son shall maintain his poor parents who are unable to earn for their life. The parents and grandparents are entitled to get maintenance from children or grand children having means. Under Hanafi Law, both son and daughter are equally accountable to care the old parents. Under Section 125(1) (d) of Code of Criminal Procedure, 1973 empowers the Magistrate to grant monthly allowance for the maintenance of parents including father and mother who are unable to maintain themselves. Son and Daughter are equally liable to pay maintenance to parents. Adoptive mother is also entitled to claim maintenance from her adopted son or daughter. Social Security Schemes including retirement benefits for the employees in formal sector or self purchased old age insurance pension schemes are also introduced. The National Level Programmes like Ministry of Road Transport and Highways along with State Government provides reservation of two seats and fare concession for senior citizens. The Ministry of Railway provide 30 % concession, facilities including separate ticket booking, wheel chairs, ramps and separate coaches. Ministry of Civil Aviation also provides discount for senior citizens. Special priority will be given to the telephone complaints registered by the Senior Citizens and people above 65 years will get 25 % or Rs 250 in NCR offers in MTNL. The Ministry of Consumer Affairs, Food and Public Distribution introduced Anthyodaya Scheme to provide 35 kgs of food grains for senior citizens living Below Poverty Line families at the rate of Rs 2 per Kg of wheat and Rs. 3 per Kg of rice. Annapoorna Scheme is implemented by the State/Union Territories to provide 10 Kgs of free food grains to those who are not covered under Old Age Pension Schemes. Health care for the elderly is implemented by Ministry of Health and Family welfare under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM). The National Programme of Health Care for Elderly (NPHCE) to provide health care facilities through primary, secondary and tertiary health care delivery systems of district hospitals in convergence with the National Health Mission, Ministry of AYUSH. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare allotted special queues in the hospitals and health care centres for registration and clinical examinations of the elderly. Special clinics at Delhi provides health checkups, operations, treatment of physically invalid, gynaecology, ENT, ophthalmology & Pathological services and Radio Therapy facilities. Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment introduced Integrated Programme for the Older Persons (IPOP) scheme in 1992 with revision in 2008 to improve the quality of life by ensuring amenities of shelter, food, medical care and entertainment opportunities. It also render 90 % of financial assistance to establishing Old Age Homes, Day Care Centres, Mobile Medical Care Units, Non Institutional Services to Older Persons, Assistance to Pandhayat Raj/Voluntary Organisations/Self Help Groups or Multi Service Centres for the elderly. Ministry of Finance introduced higher rate of interest on Savings Schemes in the Banks and Post Offices along with higher tax exemption compared to other citizens. A Central sponsored National

Social Assistance Programme (NSAP) under the Ministry of Rural Development to provide financial assistance to older persons by granting Pensions. Indira Gandhi National Old Age Pension Scheme to support elderly living below the poverty line to provide pension of Rs. 500 every month. National Help Line to help elderly with toll free number 1090 was constituted. The disbursement of Pension, Provident Fund and Gratuity was simplified with Direct Transfer System. Elder sensitive taxation policies was supported under Sec. 88 B, 88-D and 88 DDB of Income Tax Act. Special Insurance Policies like Jeevan Dhara Yojana, Jeevan Akshay Yojana, Senior Citizen Unit Yojana, Medical Insurance Yojana was introduced by Life Insurance Corporation of India (LIC). Loan facility for the elderly having low income to purchase houses constructed under Government Schemes with 10 % reservation in such allotments for the older persons. The National Programme for Health Care for Elderly, 2010 to provide preventive, curative and rehabilitative services to the elderly persons in the health care delivery system by strengthening referral systems with specialized man power and research on diseases. The Programme establish Geriatric department in 8 regional Geriatric Centres in 100 districts. Pradhan Mantri Suraksha Bima Yojana a scheme to provide one year (June-May) accidental and disability cover to all savings bank account holders between 18-70 years. It provides coverage of 2,00,000 for death or total and irrevocable loss of both eyes and 1,00,000 coverage for the loss of an eye or a limb at a premium of Rs. 12 per annum per member. Atal Pension Yojana (June 2015) scheme for those persons engage in the unorganised sector and do not have any statutory social security scheme administered through Pension Fund Regulatory and Development Authority. Any subscribers below 40 years would receive the fixed pension of Rs. 1,000- 5,000 per month payable form 60 years depending on the contribution. The government also contributes 50 % or Rs. 1000 whichever is lower to each subscriber account for five years from 2015/16 to 2019/20. The Five Year Plan (2012-2017) recommends for special health care with pension and insurance reforms with enhanced quality of life. Varishtha Pension Bima Yojana (2017) The Scheme implemented through Life Insurance Corporation for the financial inclusion and social security during old age to protect people above 60 years with an assured pension with a guaranteed return of 8 % per annum for 10 years on monthly, quarterly, half yearly or annual basis. Scheme for providing Aids and Assisted Living Devices of high quality conforming to the standards of Bureau of Indian Standards to Senior Citizens below poverty line suffering from age related disability or infirmity including low vision, hearing impairment, loss of teeth and locomotor disability. This scheme will be launched in two districts in all States and in two districts in Delhi and in one district of remaining 06 Union Territories. It is proposed to be implemented in four districts of 20 larger States, 02 districts of remaining 09 States, in NCT Delhi and in one district of other 06 Union Territories. Senior Citizens Welfare Fund (March, 2016) was constituted to be used for various welfare schemes of Senior Citizen. A Regional body called South Asia Senior Citizen's Working Group was established at the workshop on South Asia Senior Citizen's in Nepal (July 2016) on the basis of 36 point Kathmandu Declaration signed during the 18th SAARC Summit in 2014 focusing on the special needs of the elderly population in the region. It also reaffirms commitments to the Older Peoples Rights enshrined in the Vienna International Plan of Action on Ageing, The United Nations Principles for Older Persons, The Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing 2002, General Recommendation number 27 of the CEDAW Convention on the Protection of Human Rights of Older Women, 2010 and Sustainable Development Goals. The working group aims to work with the government, NGO's and civil society.

6. OBSERVATION AND FINDINGS

Majority of the respondents strongly agree that they have someone who gives them love and affection and they would like to be in company of others to be active and are not aware of opportunity provided by the Government for the senior citizens to contribute their share in the nation building and feel that there is a need for creating opportunities for the elderly to volunteer for elderly welfare in their city and all of the respondents feel safe at their home and also feel safe in their city and they feel they are easily accessible to local shops, services and facilities in their city and religious belief contributes to respondent's quality of life. We can say that the elderly people are not abused physically abused in reference to Mangalore. are not aware of the facility provided by the Senior Citizens Helpline they look forward for doing good things in their life.

7. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that very low awareness of geriatric welfare service among elderly population was present. The study highlights the need for regular awareness campaign for generating awareness among the elderly population about the benefits geriatric welfare services. The elderly women should be given the preference in formulating policies and guidelines. This study also provides the opportunity for further studies for exploration of other factors that contributes to low awareness and act as a barrier for utilization of these services so that timely and appropriate interventions can be taken to help elderly in availing benefits of these services.

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